

NOTES

Thiomalate Complexes of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III)

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THIOMALIC acid is of special interest as a sequestering agent, since it contains one mercapto group and two carboxylic groups which take part in coordination with metal ions. Earlier investigations¹⁻⁸ indicated the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 thiomalate complexes with several metal ions. It was thought worthwhile to study the thiomalate complex formation of some rare earth metal ions at different pH by pH measurement method.

Experimental

pH measurements were carried out at $31 \pm 0.5^\circ$ under nitrogen atmosphere using a Marconi pH meter. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 M by the addition of suitable amount of KNO_3 to the solution.

Results and Discussion

The amount of proton liberated during complex formation remains the same even though the metal ligand ratio is increased from 1:1.25 to 1:5, indicating the formation of a 1:1 type of complex. The reaction between M^{3+} and thiomalic acid can be represented as

where H_3TML represents thiomalic acid and C represents thiomalate complex. The charge of the complex, if any is not shown.

It can be shown as in cadmium citrate complex⁴ that,

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}]}{[\text{C}]} - \frac{a}{b} \frac{\Delta[\text{T TML}]}{[\text{C}]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \quad \dots (2)$$

where [T TML] represents the molar concentration of total thiomalate,

$$a = \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + 2 \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + 3 \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^3}$$

$$b = 1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^3}$$

Fig. 1. pH titration of 50.00 ml solution containing 5.0×10^{-4} g. mole of potassium nitrate and

- A - 3.125×10^{-4} g. moles of thiomalic acid ;
- B₁ - 3.125×10^{-4} g. moles of thiomalic acid and 2.5×10^{-4} g. moles of $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$;
- B₂ - 3.125×10^{-4} g. moles of thiomalic acid and 2.5×10^{-4} g. moles of $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$;
- B₃ - 3.125×10^{-4} g. moles of thiomalic acid and 2.5×10^{-4} g. moles of $\text{Pr}(\text{NO}_3)_3$;
- B₄ - 3.125×10^{-4} g. moles of thiomalic acid and 2.5×10^{-4} g. moles of $\text{Nd}(\text{NO}_3)_3$;
- B₅ - 3.125×10^{-4} g. moles of thiomalic acid and 2.5×10^{-4} g. moles of $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3$;
- B₆ - 3.125×10^{-4} g. moles of thiomalic acid and 2.5×10^{-4} g. moles of $\text{Gd}(\text{NO}_3)_3$;
- B₇ - 3.125×10^{-4} g. moles of thiomalic acid and 2.5×10^{-4} g. moles of $\text{Dy}(\text{NO}_3)_3$;
- B₈ - 3.125×10^{-4} g. moles of thiomalic acid and 2.5×10^{-4} g. moles of $\text{Ho}(\text{NO}_3)_3$;

against 0.1 N sodium hydroxide.

k_1 , k_2 and k_3 being the first, second and third dissociation constants¹ of thiomalic acid, respectively ($k_1 = 2.291 \times 10^{-4}$, $k_2 = 2.291 \times 10^{-5}$ and $k_3 = 1.266 \times 10^{-11}$).

The values of n are calculated at different pH values in each thiomalate system. The values of n are less than 3 below pH 6.2 for lanthanum, pH 6.0 for cerium, praseodymium and neodymium, pH 5.4 for samarium, gadolinium, dysprosium and holmium. Hence below these pH values a neutral complex C is formed in these systems with the

liberation of three protons according to equation (3).

$$K = \frac{[C][H^+]^3}{[M^{3+}][H_3TML]} \quad \dots (4)$$

The negative logarithms of the equilibrium constants for all these thiomalates are calculated by equation (4) according to the method followed in the investigation of cadmium citrate complex⁴. The mean values of $-\log K$ are found to be 12.72 ± 0.16 , 12.21 ± 0.09 , 11.55 ± 0.2 , 11.28 ± 0.14 , 11.23 ± 0.16 , 11.17 ± 0.11 , 11.15 ± 0.1 and 11.1 ± 0.06 for lanthanum, cerium, praseodymium, neodymium, samarium, gadolinium, dysprosium and holmium, respectively.

The results show that the relative order of stability for the thiomalate complexes studied in the present investigations is $La(III) < Ce(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III) < Sm(III) < Gd(III) < Dy(III) < Ho(III)$. The relative stability of these rare earth chelates increases with the decrease in the crystal radii indicating the formation of predominantly ionic complexes. The stabilities of rare earth thiomalate complexes are found to be less than those of malate complexes⁵. This corresponds to the relative order of stability as $-OH > -SH$. This is in accordance with the order reported by Rossotti⁶ and Calvin and Martell⁷.

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References

1. G. R. LENZ and A. E. MARTELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 378.
2. G. E. CHENEY, Q. FERNANDO and H. FREISER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, 63, 2055.
3. M. CEROLA, A. S. TOMPA, A. V. ORLIANO and P. S. GENTILE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 290.
4. R. K. PATNAIK and S. PANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 673.
5. N. K. MOHANTY, Ph. D. Thesis, Sambalpur University.
6. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", (Ed.) R. G. WILKINS, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1960, p. 50.
7. M. CALVIN and A. E. MARTELL, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds", Prentice Hall, Inc., N. Y., 1959, p. 170.

Some Square Planar Complexes of N-4-Methyl-7-Hydroxy-8-Acetocoumarinylidene Anthranilic Acid with Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+}

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COMPLEXES of the composition $H[M(C_{19}H_{18}NO_5)_2.Cl]$ [$M = Cu^{2+}$, Pd^{2+} or Pt^{2+}] with N-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumarinylidene anthranilic acid ($H_2MHACAA$) have been studied. Analytical, magnetic, ir and electronic spectral data show that all these complexes possess square planar configuration.

Experimental

4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl coumarin was prepared¹ and N-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumarinylidene anthranilic acid, a tridentate ligand, was prepared by refluxing a mixture of 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl coumarin and anthranilic acid in ethanol in presence of a few drops of glacial acetic acid on water bath for 5.0 hr^{2,3}, yield 75%, m.p. 155°. (Found : C, 66.80 ; H, 4.30 ; N, 4.00. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{18}NO_5$; C, 67.65 ; H, 4.45 ; N, 4.15%). 75% ethanolic solutions of the ligand were used throughout. Metal chlorides of A. R. quality were used.

The complexes of Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+} were isolated by refluxing a stoichiometric mixture of metal chloride and ligand in ethanol solution on the water bath for 2.5-4.5 hr. On refrigeration for a few days the reaction mixture yielded brown, grey and yellow crystals of the complexes which were washed with water, ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum, yield 60-70%, decomposition point 180-213°.

The complexes were analysed for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen on Thomas CH Analyser-35 and Colemann N-Analyser-29 at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Copper was determined by titration with EDTA using fast sulphon black indicator⁴. The metals, Pd and Pt, were determined gravimetrically as DMG or ammonium chloroplatinate complexes.

(a) $H[Cu(C_{19}H_{18}NO_5)_2.Cl]$, brown compound. (Found : C, 52.20 ; H, 3.00 ; N, 3.08 ; Cl, 8.03 ; Cu, 14.29. Calcd. ; C, 52.41 ; H, 3.21 ; N, 3.21 ; Cl, 8.16 ; Cu, 14.58%).

(b) $H[Pd(C_{19}H_{18}NO_5)_2.Cl]$, grey compound. (Found : C, 47.63 ; H, 2.73 ; N, 2.69 ; Cl, 7.25 ; Pd, 22.07. Calcd. ; C, 47.78 ; H, 2.92 ; N, 2.92 ; Cl, 7.42 ; Pd, 22.26%).

(c) $H[Pt(C_{19}H_{18}NO_5)_2.Cl]$, yellow compound. (Found : C, 40.00 ; H, 2.30 ; N, 2.28 ; Cl, 6.09 ;

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